

NANOSCALE SYNCHROTRON XRF STUDY OF THE ‘RUST’ IN THE APOLLO 16 SAMPLE 66095 ‘RUSTY ROCK’ IMMEDIATELY AFTER FIRST EXPOSURE TO EARTH’S ATMOSPHERE. M. Martínez¹, F. E. Brenker¹, J. Herthogs², T. Baert², B. Vekemans², L. Vincze², M. Burghammer³, R. Tucoulou³, ¹Schwiete Cosmochemistry Laboratory, Dept. of Geoscience, Goethe University Frankfurt, Altenhoferallee 1, 60438 Frankfurt, Germany (MartinezJimenez@em.uni-frankfurt.de), ²XMI Research group, Ghent University De Pintelaan 270, S12, B-9000 Ghent, Belgium (Thibaut.Baert@UGent.be), ³ESRF-The European Synchrotron, 71 avenue des Martyrs, 38043 Grenoble Cedex 9, France.

Introduction: The Apollo sample 66095, also called ‘Rusty Rock’, is the most volatile-rich lunar sample returned by the Apollo Program. It was collected by the Apollo 16 crew at the Caylay Plains from a cm-block on the south rim of a 10 m crater near the base of the Stone Mountain. The sample was first noted for its distinctive in-site brown-yellow stain rust surrounding iron metal.

Rusty rock is a unique impact-melt breccia associated with fumarolic activity [1]. It is interpreted to have formed through condensation from a cooling gas from an ancient impact-generated lunar fumarole in a low-H system [1] at 580 ± 50 °C [2]. 66095 and Apollo 16 soils are enriched in the volatiles Cl and S, as well as in moderately volatile trace metals Tl, Br, Cd, Sn, Zn, Pb, Rb, Cs, Ga, B, and Li [1], [3], [4], [5].

Sample 66095 represents an exceptional example of a volatile-rich lunar surface rock in which volatiles were inherited through vapor condensation from an originally volatile-poor lunar interior source during the thermomagmatic evolution of the Moon [1]. Samples associated with volcanic activity are significantly valuable because they serve to better understand the origin and characteristics of interior lunar volatile reservoirs and their behavior during transport and eruption onto the lunar surface, primarily by basaltic magmatism (e.g., [1], [6], [7], [8]).

The origin of the chloride-containing iron oxyhydroxides (akaganeite, goethite) or the ‘rust’ in 66095 remains a key open question. It is still unclear whether these minerals formed on the lunar surface or resulted from contamination after collection of the sample.

Here, we investigate the rust immediately after exposure to Earth’s atmosphere to provide additional insights into the origin of volatile reservoirs on the Moon, their interactions, and how they are altered by the Earth’s atmosphere, which have important implications not only into the overall evolution of the Moon, but also for handling lunar-volatile samples to be returned by the Artemis IV mission.

Samples: Three 2-mm sized rock chips from sub-sample ,436, numbered 66095,475 (0,04 g), 66095,476 (0,03 g), and 66095,477 (0,02 g), were prepared in an atmospheric controlled environment at Johnson Space Center (JSC). Since their collection on the Moon, the samples were kept in a pristine N₂ atmosphere. The three rock chips were sealed in borosilicate glass containers under a pristine N₂

atmosphere and wrapped in double Teflon bags at JSC. The samples were received in June 2024.

Methodology: In July 2024, samples 66095,475 and 66095,477 were briefly opened for ~1 second to allow interaction with the terrestrial atmosphere. After 5 months of this exposure, sample ,475 was petrographically polished and studied by SEM, EPMA, and TEM at Goethe University [9], whereas 66095,477 was kept as a rock chip. At the time of the present experiment, 66095,477 had interacted with Earth’s atmosphere for 1 year and ~7 months, while sample 66095,476 remained stored in pristine N₂ atmosphere.

In March 2026, samples 66095,477 and 66095,476 were investigated by synchrotron X-ray fluorescence and X-ray diffraction at ID13 beamline of the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) in Grenoble. The beam energy was set to 20 keV, with a beam size of approximately 100 nm x 100 nm (HxV). Sample 66095,477 was placed inside a quartz capillary with a 2.5 mm diameter in the upper part and 1 mm diameter in the lower part, with a wall thickness of 0.01 mm. The sample positioned at the transition between the wider and the narrower part of the capillary. A roll of ultralene thin film was inserted in the upper part to prevent any movement during analysis. Sample 66095,476 was opened and exposed to terrestrial air for the first time on March 13th, 2026. The sample was wrapped in ultralene thin film (4µm thickness) and one end of the film was rolled and inserted into a quartz capillary, 3 mm in diameter in the upper part and 2.5 mm diameter in the lower part. The wrapped sample remained outside the capillary, acting as a ‘free standing’ rock chip during the measurements. Several high-resolution scans were acquired over a region of interest, 200 x 200 µm, to investigate the nanoscale chemistry and mineral phases. These scans (between 3 to 10 hours each) were repeated over three consecutive days to monitor potential changes in the elemental distribution of volatiles within the rusty region resulting from hydration and/or oxidation from terrestrial air.

Results:

Sample 66095,475. Previous work has shown that this sample contains two different occurrences of Cl-rich akaganeite associated with Fe,Ni metal: (i) as an amorphous phase (2.77-4.14 wt% Cl) in direct contact with the metal grain, associated with stanfieldite and chromite; and (ii) as a vein, ~3.5 µm x ~1 µm in size,

containing up to 20 wt% Cl in some regions and containing irregular Ni-rich sub-veins [10].

Sample 66095,477. Results are still preliminary. During initial investigations, several scans of varying sizes and resolutions were performed. The results in this sample showed that fluorescence from the low energy elements S and Cl were blocked by the quartz capillary. Therefore, a different method was applied for the sealed sample.

Sample 66095,476. Results are still preliminary. After 5 hours of sample exposure, a region of interest, 200 x 200 μm , targeting the rust, was identified, showing the presence of FeNi metal with morphologies ranging from elongated and rounded to euhedral, from a few nm up to 200 μm in size, associated with the volatiles Cl and S. Other elements associated in this area include Ti, Cr, Cu, Br, Sr, Y, and Zr (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Synchrotron XRF images of selected elements detected in the rusty alteration of 66095,476.

Discussion: Nanoscale analysis of volatile-rich lunar samples is fundamental to prepare for the Artemis IV mission, which is planned to collect volatile-

rich samples from the lunar south pole in 2028 and return them for laboratory studies on Earth. Akageneite, a Cl-bearing iron oxyhydroxide (the ‘rust’), is of particular interest, because it has been interpreted to form through oxidation and hydration of lawrencite (FeCl_2) upon exposure to the terrestrial atmosphere [1].

Our TEM observations in 66095,475 may support a terrestrial origin for akageneite. However, no lawrencite was identified. This could indicate that lawrencite was completely consumed after 5 months of exposure to the terrestrial air. Alternatively, akageneite may have formed on the Moon if the lunar gas changed from Cl-dominant to OH-dominant. Our TEM observations also suggest that volatile elements can migrate several microns through fractures and veins within the sample.

The XRF and XRD datasets obtained during the synchrotron experiment are still being processed. If akageneite is detected in the earliest scans of sample 66095,476, this would suggest either that the mineral formed on the Moon or that alteration occurred within the first 5 hours after exposure to terrestrial atmosphere. If akageneite instead appears only in later scans, the results could provide a time constraint for alteration of lawrencite in the order of 1-3 days. Alternatively, if only lawrencite and/or other metal chlorides are identified in 66095,476, this would support a terrestrial origin for the rust formation occurring over longer timescales than a few days.

Conclusions: The present study aims to better constrain the original, volatile-rich mineral phases present in pristine lunar samples and to understand how they alter after exposure to Earth’s atmosphere. This work addresses several important unresolved questions: how fast does this alteration occur? (i.e., how long does it take for lawrencite to hydrate and oxidize into chlorine-rich iron oxyhydroxides — hours, days, or months?). In addition, what is the spatial extent of this alteration? For example, is it restricted to areas immediately surrounding metal grains, or can volatile species migrate and affect other regions of the sample over time? Constraining the timescales and spatial extent of this alteration will be crucial for study and preservation of future volatile-rich returned by the Artemis IV mission.

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